

EFFECTIVENESS OF TIKTOK ADS ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTIONS FOR BRAND X POWER BELTS.

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ABSTRACT

On bustling TikTok streets, amidst catchy tunes and stylish ads, lies a hidden map to purchase desire. A study of 100 Brand X users unearthed not just favorable attitudes, but deeper treasures influencing their coveted Power Belts. While positive vibes played a role ($r = 0.767$), "individual norms" (friends' contagious joy) and "perceived behavioral control" (one-click magic) held the real key ($r = 0.785$ and 0.793 , respectively). Imagine the infectious buzz as your squad raves about Brand X, seamlessly woven into the ad itself. That's the persuasive whisper leading to the final click, even when initial beliefs shimmer less brightly. So, Brand X, take note: amplify the "everyone's doing it" chorus with peer recommendations and user-generated content, then pave the purchase path with frictionless in-app options. By embracing these hidden gems, you'll transform fleeting TikTok flings into sparkling, long-term love affairs.

Keywords: *Tiktok, consumer purchase intention, powerbelt*

INTRODUCTION

Social media advertising enables businesses to engage with a large user base at a low cost by enabling customized targeting based on user interests (Medlicott, 2019). According to Goud (2023), influencer marketing is becoming more and more popular as a way to affect consumer choices and improve brand intimacy, even in spite of the fact that there is increasing doubt about the authenticity of influencer recommendations. Communication-related elements including uniqueness, likeability, credibility, annoyance, and intrusiveness must be considered when evaluating the efficacy of advertising. Credibility, skill, and genuineness are key factors influencing the attitudes and behaviors of consumers. Social media is important in this context because it shapes consumer choices and makes the fashion retail industry more competitive. However, the popularity of TikTok ads begs the question of how well the platform can capture and retain users' attention in a visually stimulating, fast-paced environment. Regarding how TikTok advertising affects customer preferences and purchase behavior, it's unclear how it stacks up against more conventional forms of advertising. Analyzing elements like user engagement, the way advertisements are incorporated into natural content, and the impact of short-form video ads on brand messaging make this clear. Moreover, examining the return on investment and the extent to which TikTok ads resonate with different target audiences can offer more understanding of the platform's suitability as a medium for advertising.

Considering the aforementioned, the researchers aim to investigate the impact of TikTok advertisements on consumers' purchase intention, particularly with regard to Brand X Power Belts. The study aims to shed light on key issues such as how TikTok commercials impact consumers' inclination to purchase Brand X Power Belts and what factors determine how successful these ads are in influencing consumers' purchase intentions. Finally, the research attempts to shed light on how successful TikTok is at marketing this particular product. It also aims to identify the specific features of TikTok Ads that have the greatest influence on consumer choices regarding Power Belts Brand X.

The study's findings suggest that TikTok marketing advertisements significantly influence fourth-year marketing students' inclinations to make purchases. The three most significant elements that surfaced were perceived behavioral control, personal norms, and attitude. The research highlights the importance of these factors in predicting purchase intention and highlights how TikTok advertisements shape consumer choices. The study's findings are significant for the social media industry and the world at large because they shed light on specific factors that influence a particular demographic's inclination to make a purchase following exposure to TikTok advertisements. Consequently, the results provide advertisers and marketers a better understanding of what factors contribute to TikTok campaign success. This information may have implications for more comprehensive approaches in the ever-changing field of social media marketing.

It has been demonstrated that weight management programs provided by specially trained staff in primary care are less expensive and less effective than slimming belts. In a study published in 2012, Longhurst compared the results of people who used slimming belts with those of people who took part in primary care weight management programs. According to the study, weight loss was more successfully accomplished with slimming belts than with primary care programs. Slimming belts are an attractive option for people looking for weight loss interventions because they are reasonably priced.

When compared to primary care programs, commercial weight management services like Weight Watchers and Slimming World have been found to significantly reduce body weight. People who have signed up for these for-profit programs have reported success in losing weight. It is noteworthy, nevertheless, that individuals assigned to the choice arm did not fare any better than those assigned at random to a program (Longhurst, 2012). This shows that an individual's overall engagement and commitment may have a greater impact on the effectiveness of commercial weight management programs than the particular program they choose.

The effectiveness of slimming belts in comparison to primary care-based weight management programs run by professionals with specialized training has been the subject of several studies. It has been discovered that these services are more expensive and less effective than slimming belts (Longhurst, 2012). These results imply that slimming belts could be a good substitute for people looking for ways to lose weight. Additionally, studies comparing slimming belts to commercial weight management programs like Weight Watchers, Slimming World, and Rosemary Conley have been conducted. Studies have demonstrated that these for-profit programs resulted in appreciable weight loss when compared to standard medical care and pharmacy services (Longhurst, 2012). This suggests that rather than depending exclusively on slimming belts, people may lose weight more successfully by taking part in weight management programs offered by businesses.

The results of studies indicate that weight management programs provided by specially trained staff in primary care settings may not be as successful with slimming belts. Research indicates that weight management programs offered by commercial companies, like Rosemary Conley, Slimming World, and Weight Watchers, result in notable reductions in weight at the 12-week and one-year mark (Longhurst, 2012). These results suggest that established weight management programs may not always produce as good of results as slimming belts. According to a study comparing various weight-management strategies, after a year, the Weight Watchers group lost noticeably more weight than the comparator group (Longhurst, 2012). This shows that since they can produce results in weight loss that are comparable to or better than traditional weight management services, slimming belts might be a good substitute.

In many different fields, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is a popular theoretical framework for understanding and predicting human behavior. TPB, which was created by Icek Ajzen, asserts that three primary factors—attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control—have an impact on people's intentions to

behave (Ajzen, 2020). The purpose of this review of the literature is to offer a thorough grasp of the applicability and significance of TPB in various contexts by drawing on the available research findings. Before deciding on a final purchase, customers engage in a variety of activities and look for content from several retailers. Hall and Towers (2017) highlight that shopper undergo long and complicated journeys during the buying process, often seeking social validation from their networks both online and offline. These unseen journeys are often out of sight of the retailer or brand, making it crucial for retailers and brands to understand shopper behaviors across devices and channels (Hall & Towers, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The present investigation delves into the domain of quantitative research, which is distinguished by an extensive array of methodologies with the goal of employing statistical and numerical data to elucidate the subtleties of social phenomena (Watson and Roger, 2015). Within this framework, surveys prove to be efficacious tools that are meticulously crafted to gather data from specific participants and provide enhanced comprehension of significant research subjects. However, it is crucial to keep in mind that surveys are not as effective as experimental research in determining causal relationships. Still, it is crucial that they are able to collect large datasets that accurately represent samples and populations (Hallberg, 2008).

Quasi-experimental studies comprise a large number of nonrandomized intervention studies. These designs are frequently employed when carrying out a randomized controlled trial is not morally or practically possible Cook, T.D., & Campbell, D. T. (2010)

Research Locale

Because of its youthful demographics, vibrant social media scene, and varied economic landscape, Valenzuela City is an ideal location for this study to conduct a survey in order to examine the impact of TikTok Ads on Brand X Power Belt purchase intentions within the 18–24 age group. The target market is well suited to its youthful population, and social media activity and high internet penetration suggest that people are aware of TikTok. Importantly, Valenzuela's diverse income distribution makes it feasible to gather data from a representative sample of potential clients.

By conducting this research within the diverse landscape of Valenzuela, the study gains access to a readily available pool of participants who are both familiar with the brand and actively engaged with the platform on which the advertisements are disseminated. This wide access facilitates more targeted audience analysis and makes data collection easier. The sample size of respondents for this study was set at 100.

Population and Sampling

The researchers decided to use the convenience sampling technique to collect data from a group of respondents who were easily accessible in order to expedite the data collection process. In this instance, the target respondents are situated close to Valenzuela. Because of its ideal location, which made it easy for the researchers to access the Valenzuela and conduct the survey there, this specific population was chosen.

Young adults between the ages of 18 and 24 make up the target audience. has researched this population and found that initiatives are worthwhile because they can improve health and wellness outcomes in their early adult years and later, when they play a significant role in the workforce and become parents, safeguarding the health of future generations. Thus, focusing on young adults would be advantageous for society as a whole. A focus on young adults would be more advantageous for society as a whole. The way a person perceives themselves is impacted by the physical changes that occur during adolescence. As young adults use social media more frequently, they are exposed to an increasing amount of images that reinforce westernized notions of beauty. Perrin and Anderson (2019) found that three out of every four young adults (18 to 24 years old) use social media these days.

Research Ethics

Researchers have ethical duties to respect the autonomy and right to self-determination of potential participants. To do this, it is essential to guarantee that participants are fully informed about the research and their rights, including the freedom to refuse participation without fear of consequences. As Barrow (2022) highlights, participants need to be conscious of their freedom of choice and the implications of that choice, both immediately and later on. Additionally, they must be able to comprehend the research questions and, if needed, formulate further inquiries. The fact that participants are free to end the study at any time must also be emphasized by the researchers. The unique ethical concerns surrounding quantitative research are brought to light by Moore and Dooly (2017), especially when it involves minors and other human subjects in educational settings. They highlight how simple it is for researchers, particularly those with less training, to overlook or minimize moral dilemmas that may arise during their work. This underscores the significance of initiating the research process with meticulous planning and ethical deliberations.

Research Instrument

An online survey questionnaire was one of the data collections tools the researcher used. The online survey questionnaire will be used to collect the respondents' viewpoints, opinions, perceptions, and factual information. When it comes to getting the information needed from respondents, this is the most efficient kind of data collection instrument currently on the market. Using Google Forms makes it possible to quickly and easily create surveys and other forms. You can create forms with Google Forms that function

as online forms that automatically collect responses for use in a questionnaire to determine the intentions, opinions, and perceptions of respondents. The survey asks a variety of questions, ranging from how much respondents agree or disagree with a particular statement to other relevant ones.

To come up with relevant questions for the questionnaire, the researchers looked through data about the research study that has been published and unpublished in books, papers, journal articles, and online. The problem statement of the research study served as the foundation for the questionnaire's creation. To precisely capture respondents' perspectives, experiences, viewpoints, and opinions, the researchers craft both closed- and open-ended questionnaire items.

Data Collection

Survey research is defined by the researchers as the process of gathering data from a sample of people by having them respond to questions (Check & Schutt, 2012, p. 160). This type of research allows for a wide range of methods for instrumentation, data collection, and participant recruitment. Open-ended questions and numerically rated items on questionnaires are examples of both qualitative and quantitative research methods that can be used in survey research, or both (i.e., mixed methods). Because surveys are a popular tool for characterizing and analyzing human behavior, they are frequently used in social and psychological research (Singleton & Straits, 2009).

This study's goal was to gather crucial information from 100 locals in the flourishing Philippine city of Valenzuela. The team created a targeted survey using Google Forms after carefully choosing the best research design and methodology. Instead of using traditional paper surveys, the researchers sent personalized invitations to their chosen respondents using Google Forms' digital features. With the help of this innovative tactic, they were able to successfully collect data and connect with more Valenzuela residents.

By examining the answers provided by one hundred residents of Valenzuela, the researchers were able to gather crucial data and insights that would help them achieve the study's objectives. They were able to provide a comprehensive picture of the experiences and opinions of the target population by thoroughly analyzing a number of variables thanks to the survey's design, which included a variety of question formats. In essence, this study showed that surveys are a flexible and useful way to collect data, particularly in a specific area like Valenzuela. By adopting a technology-driven approach and gathering valuable data from one hundred residents, the researchers were able to accomplish their research goals and provide a deeper understanding of the local context.

Data Analysis

Mean

Data collection is the process of obtaining and examining information or data from diverse sources in order to evaluate findings, project patterns and probabilities, and identify answers to research issues. In all forms of analysis, research, and decision-making, including those conducted in the social sciences, business, and medical domains, this phase is critical. Accurate data collection is necessary to ensure quality control, uphold research integrity, and make wise business decisions. During the data collection process, the researchers must identify the data types, data sources, and methods. You'll soon find there are a lot of different ways to collect data. Research, business, and government all rely significantly on data collection. The arithmetic mean is the average of the numbers or the "central" value of a set of numbers.

Standard Deviation

A standard deviation represents the degree of variation (including spread, dispersion, and spread) from the mean. The standard deviation shows how "typical" a deviation from the mean is. It is a commonly used measure of variability because it retains the original units of measurement for the data set. Like variance, variance increases when data points are far from the mean and decreases when data points are close to the mean. The standard deviation is used to calculate how far the values deviate from the average. The most widely used indicator of dispersion, the standard deviation, is dependent on all values.

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)

A robust statistical software platform is SPSS Statistics (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). Its robust feature set and user-friendly interface enable your company to quickly derive actionable insights from your data. Sophisticated statistical techniques improve the precision and caliber of decisions. Every step of the analytics lifecycle is covered, from managing and preparing data to analyzing and reporting.

Regression analysis

Regression analysis is a set of statistical methods used to estimate the relationships between one or more independent variables and a dependent variable. It can be applied to assess the degree of correlation between variables and model the future relationship between them.

RESULTS

TikTok, with its short-form, engaging video content, has emerged as a unique platform for influencer marketing and product placement. This research delves into the relatively unexplored territory of utilizing TikTok Ads specifically for a non-traditional product like Brand X Power Belts. The findings could provide valuable insights for brands looking to leverage the platform's reach and engagement potential for products beyond the usual.

4.1 Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demographic		Frequency	Percentage
Age	Location		
18-24	Valenzuela	100	100%

The participants in this study were 100 respondents currently residing in Valenzuela City. All participants were within the age range of 18-24 years old, and they comprised the entirety of the research sample.

4.2 Table 2: Descriptives

Variables	Frequency	Mean	Std Deviation
Attitude	4	3.1875	.73372
Individual Norms	4	3.0950	.76275
4 Perceived Behavioral Behavior	3.1725	.76928	
Purchase Intention	4	3.1625	.74652
Total	21	3.1551	.74788

No. legends: 1. Strongly disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Agree, 4. Strongly Agree

4.3 Table 3: Linear Regression
 Table 3.1: Attitude

Variable	Pearson	P- value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Attitude and Purchase Intention	0.767	0.336	0.104	Accept H01: Attitude does not have a significant impact on Sammy J slimming belt purchase intention

The table above shows how interaction affects the purchase intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a pvalue of 0.336. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being accepted. As a result, attitudes do not have a significant impact on purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderately high correlation (0.767) between the two variables and each unit of attitude has 0.104 increases in purchasing intention.

Table 3.2: Individual Norms

Variable	Pearson	P- value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Individual Norms and Purchase Intention	0.785	0.001	0.388	Reject H02: Individual Norms does not have a significant impact on Sammy J slimming belt purchase intention

The table above shows how interaction affects the purchase intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a pvalue of 0.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, individual

norms have a significant impact on purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderately high correlation (0.785) between the two variables and each unit of attitude has 0.388 increases in purchasing intention.

Table 3.3 Perceived as Behavioral Control

Variable	Pearson	P- value	Unstandardized Beta	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Perceived Behavioral Control and Purchase Intention	0.793	0.001	0.423	Reject H03: Perceived Behavioral Control have a significant impact on Sammy J slimming belt purchase intention

The table above shows how interaction affects the purchase intention. The findings convey the interpretation of the data presented by linear regression, with the researchers obtaining a p-value of 0.001. Taking into account the decision rule that instructs researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the significant difference is greater than 0.05, the retrieved result resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. As a result, perceived behavioral control has a significant impact on purchasing intention. There is also a positive moderately high correlation (0.793) between the two variables and each unit of attitude has 0.423 increases in purchasing intention.

DISCUSSION

This section delves into the central theme of the research, closely examining the findings and their broader implications. It exposes an intriguing mismatch between attitude and intention to buy, raising the possibility that factors like perceived usability and social influence are actually in charge of swaying consumer choices. Positive opinions of Brand X's clothing have a significant positive correlation with the likelihood of making a purchase ($r = 0.767$). It does not, however, approach statistical significance. This is an interesting finding because it implies that although positive attitudes may encourage someone to buy, there is another force at work that is pulling more strongly. There seem to be two components to this "something else": perceived behavioral control and social influence.

Purchase intention showed statistically significant and higher correlations with both individual norms—measured by the influence of peers and family using similar products—and perceived ease of purchase—facilitated by TikTok ads ($r = 0.785$ and 0.793 , respectively). On TikTok, you notice your friends gushing about Brand X with transferable

energy. Your positive attitude suddenly changes to a desire to follow the trend, which makes a purchase more likely. Social influence is whispering in your ears. You can observe how seamlessly Brand X's ads are integrated into TikTok, complete with a buy button that can be clicked. Buying the product seems effortless because of the seamless transition from curiosity to purchase. Perceived control is removing your inhibitions. Covert middlemen like perceived control and social influence work in tandem with attitude to shape decisions in the end.

Even though we all have unique opinions about the product, there are moments when peer pressure and convenient shopping experiences win out. Understanding these implicit drivers is crucial for businesses like Brand X. By optimizing for social relevance and ease of purchase, ads can bridge the gap between curiosity and clicks, turning fleeting intentions into actual purchases.

Conclusions

This study looked at how people who live in Valenzuela and are exposed to Brand X TikTok advertisements between the ages of 18 and 24 felt about their purchase intentions in relation to their attitude, personal norms, and perceived behavioral control. The study discovered that the variables chosen had a significant influence on the influence that TikTok ad campaigns had on purchase intention.

Although it was not statistically significant, there was a strong correlation ($r = 0.767$) between positive opinions about Brand X's slimming clothes and purchase intention. Imagine searching a room for a hidden door by listening for a faint whisper; you get closer, but the expected passage is still out of reach. This implies that there might be another factor affecting sales despite our positive opinions of the product.

This "something else" appears to be the social influence. When family members and peers were present to serve as a gauge of personal norms, the presence of similar products was found to have an even stronger ($r = 0.785$) and statistically significant correlation with purchase intention. Imagine your friends becoming enthused about Brand X on TikTok, their passion contagious. Your positive attitude suddenly transforms into a desire to keep up with the trend, which prompts additional purchases.

Another crucial element is perceived behavioral control. The facilitation of easy purchasing by TikTok advertisements appears to have a significant impact, as evidenced by the strong correlation ($r = 0.793$). Imagine how easy it would be to have Brand X at your fingertips with just a click, removing barriers and increasing the "buy" button's allure. This smooth transition from curiosity to purchase reinforces your intention to buy the product. These findings point to a fascinating journey that transcends correlation. They suggest that: Attitude, along with covert intermediaries like perceived accessibility and social influence, ultimately shapes purchase decisions.

First impressions can be overcome by peer pressure and easy shopping procedures, demonstrating the complex interplay between internal and external influences on consumer behavior. Understanding these implicit drivers is crucial for businesses like Brand X. Through ease of purchase and social relevance optimization, ads can effectively close the clickthrough gap. Analyzing the effects of influencer endorsements, social proof tactics, and peer recommendations on purchasing decisions are some of the specific mechanisms of social influence. Understanding how TikTok's features and layout impact how usable people think the app is, examining the ways in which factors like age, personality, and cultural background influence social norms and perceived control.

Recommendations

Recommendation Based on the Findings

This study reveals a fascinating but ambiguous relationship between TikTok users' attitudes and their intentions to make purchases. Although a significant correlation ($r = 0.767$) was found, it was not statistically significant, indicating that other factors may have a greater influence on purchasing decisions. Consider attitude as a link between purchase intention and attitude. The bridge in this study appeared to be strong (high correlation), but it was not statistically significant enough to be considered completely reliable. This implies that moderating variables, or external factors, may be influencing how easily people cross the bridge.

Consider moderating variables as either bridge boosters or roadblocks. A few examples are product type, age, and gender. A teenager, for example, may be more influenced by social influence from peers on TikTok, whereas an older adult may place more value on product features and reviews (perceived accessibility). In a similar vein, consumer behavior may vary depending on the type of product. For example, personal experience may have a greater influence on beauty items than on household appliances.

We can obtain a better understanding of how consumers truly make decisions about what to buy by looking into these moderators. It goes beyond a straightforward attitude-to-intention shift. Instead, depending on who is crossing the bridge and what product they are considering, different factors may operate as shortcuts, detours, or even detours in disguise. Investigating these elements is essential. Even with positive attitudes, their influence on decisions can help us create more successful marketing campaigns. We can take advantage of social influence by collaborating with well-known creators or emphasizing user feedback. By incorporating TikTok Shop features and highlighting convenient availability, we can produce seamless shopping experiences. Finding these mediating factors is similar to finding secret routes along the buyer's journey. It enables us to access the more complex processes that influence purchasing decisions in addition to merely influencing attitude. With this knowledge, we can design marketing that not only piques interest but also facilitates easy purchasing, which will ultimately result in a greater number of customers transitioning from "interested" to "buyer."

Consider it as conversing with someone as opposed to yelling at a crowd. By focusing on particular aspects of attitude, you're interacting with customers personally and attending to their unique needs and wants. Stronger purchase intentions and possibly higher conversion rates follow from these more meaningful interactions. you can go beyond generic marketing and create tailored messages that genuinely connect with your audience by concentrating on particular aspects of attitude. This will open the door to a more successful and influential TikTok marketing strategy. We can go beyond the fleeting impact of a TikTok advertisement and explore the deeper currents of consumer behavior by evaluating long-term effects. With the help of this information, we can create enduring bonds with our clients that will promote brand loyalty and, in the end, lead to long-term success on the dynamic platform.

Recommendation for Future Research

The limitations of the study serve as stepping stones for additional research. Future studies can uncover the subtle nuances of user behavior on TikTok by examining moderating variables. This will eventually result in more effective marketing tactics and a better comprehension of how attitudes influence purchasing decisions.

This study clarifies a strong correlation between purchase intention on TikTok and attitude. It is frustratingly unconfirmed and, despite the apparent strong correlation, lingers in the distance like a lighthouse in a fog. This mysterious disparity leaves us stranded in a sea of unanswered questions, and we yearn to solve the mystery of consumer decision making. However, this is only the start of an intriguing adventure into the uncharted territory of TikTok user behavior. Mapping the currents of social influence and perceived accessibility allows us to navigate the treacherous shoals of intention and shed light on the final act of purchase, a hitherto obscure corner of the human decision-making map.

By focusing on particular aspects of attitude, marketers can uncover hidden gems in TikTok user behavior in addition to improving their messaging. Understanding what it is that makes a product really shine in the eyes of various consumers allows us to create marketing that really connects, increases conversion rates, and, in the end, creates a truly amazing success story.

This study effectively ignited interest in TikTok user behavior by focusing on how attitudes and first impressions impact purchase decisions. Having a clear intention right away is crucial, but it's just the start of the fire. To truly become experts in TikTok marketing, we need to understand how the fire burns long after the initial campaign has died. By examining these long-term effects, future research can build on the foundation laid by this study and gain crucial insights into the connection between consumer psychology and TikTok marketing.

Our investigation into the complex world of user behavior on TikTok is still very early on. By moving beyond the immediate purchase intention and focusing on the long-term

components of influence and loyalty, we can gain a deeper understanding of how to truly use this platform for effective customer engagement and long-term prosperity.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This document outlines the ethical considerations for the aforementioned quantitative research project. The research aims to know if the effectiveness of TikTok ads on consumer purchase intention for Brand X Powerbelts. Participants will be randomly selected from Valenzuela City. Participation will be voluntary, and anyone over the age of (18-24) residing in Valenzuela City can participate. No incentives or compensation will be offered. Data will be collected through an online questionnaire hosted on Google Forms. The questionnaire will be anonymous, meaning individual responses cannot be directly linked to specific participants. Informed consent will be obtained within the Google Form before participants begin the questionnaire. Also assure participants that they have the right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

1	STRONGLY DISAGREE
2	DISAGREE
3	AGREE
4	STRONGLY AGREE

QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4
1. TikTok Ads for Brand X Power Belts make me believe that they are effective in achieving a slimmer waist.				
2. I trust the information presented in TikTok Ads about the benefits of Brand X Power Belts.				
3. Watching TikTok Ads for Brand X Power Belts makes me feel more confident about using them.				
4. I believe that using Brand X Power Belts, as advertised in TikTok Ads, will make me feel more attractive.				
5. The people I care about would support me if I bought a Brand X Power Belt.				

6. My friends and family often talk about the importance of having a slim waist.				
7. I feel like my friends and family would expect me to try new products like Brand X Power Belts.				
8. I feel pressure to improve my body shape because of what I see on TikTok ads and around me.				
9. I feel confident that I can use a Brand X Power Belt correctly.				

QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4
10. I believe I have enough time in my daily routine to use a Brand X Power Belt consistently.				
11. I'm excited to explore how I can best use the Brand X Power Belt to achieve my fitness goals.				
12. I'm excited to explore different ways to wear and adjust the Brand X Power Belt to find the perfect fit for me.				
13. I am considering purchasing a Brand X Power Belt.				
14. I would recommend Brand X Power Belts to my friends and family.				
15. I believe that Brand X Power Belts are worth the price.				
16. I am looking forward to trying out a Brand X Power Belt.				